

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of transparency, accountability, and participation on the effectiveness of school management. The study employed a mixed methods approach with a sequential explanatory design, involving the collection and analysis of quantitative data, followed by qualitative data to deepen the research findings. The sample consisted of 43 respondents, consisting of principals, teachers, and administrative staff from several public and private schools. Data collection techniques included questionnaires, interviews, and documentation. The quantitative analysis showed that transparency, accountability, and participation simultaneously had a significant influence on the effectiveness of school management. However, only participation had a significant effect, while transparency and accountability did not. The coefficient determination test showed that the three variables explained 76.6% of the variation in school management effectiveness. The qualitative analysis revealed that participation was the primary factor influencing the effectiveness of school management, due to the active involvement of teachers and education staff in program planning, implementation, and evaluation. Meanwhile, transparency and accountability have been implemented but tend to be administrative in nature and have not been optimally utilized in decision-making. Data integration shows that the effectiveness of school management is more influenced by active participation than by formal transparency and accountability. Therefore, improving the quality of participation is key to achieving effective school management.

Keywords: transparency, accountability, participation, effectiveness of school management, mix methods.

INTRODUCTION

The demand for improving the quality of education focuses not only on the learning aspect but also on the governance of educational institutions. In this context, the application of good governance principles is a strategic approach to improving the effectiveness of school management. The principles of good governance, which encompass transparency, accountability, and participation, are believed to create a more open, responsible, and participatory management system. In the public sector, the application of these principles aims to increase public trust and prevent irregularities in resource management. The application of good governance principles in education management has become a crucial focus for improving the quality of public services. Transparency, accountability, and participation are key elements contributing to the effectiveness of educational organizations (Mulyono et al., 2021).

Several studies have shown that transparency in school management significantly impacts organizational trust and performance (Sari & Nugroho, 2020). Meanwhile, accountability plays a role in ensuring the efficient use of resources and in line with organizational goals (Pratama et al., 2022). However, stakeholder participation often remains a formality and has not yet optimally impacted the quality of decision-making (Hidayat & Rahman, 2021). The implementation of good governance principles in school management still faces various obstacles. Several

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

studies show that transparency often remains administrative in nature, while stakeholder participation has not yet been fully implemented substantively. Furthermore, principal leadership and organizational culture also influence the success of these principles.

Furthermore, there are differences in characteristics between public and private schools in terms of organizational structure and decision-making mechanisms, which have the potential to impact governance implementation. Based on these conditions, this study aims to analyze the implementation of good governance principles in high school management and explain the dynamics that occur through a mixed-methods approach.

Research Objectives

This study aims to:

1. Analyzing the application of good governance principles (transparency, accountability, and participation) in the management of public and private senior high schools in East Kalimantan.
2. Integrating quantitative and qualitative findings to provide a comprehensive picture of the relationship between good governance principles and school management effectiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Good Governance in Education Management

The concept of good governance refers to governance that emphasizes transparency, accountability, participation, effectiveness, and the rule of law. In the context of education, these principles form the basis for managing schools as public institutions that manage resources for the benefit of the community. The implementation of good governance in education aims to improve service quality, budget efficiency, and accountability to stakeholders.

Transparency

Transparency is the openness in providing relevant and easily accessible information to stakeholders. In school management, transparency is demonstrated through the open disclosure of information regarding school programs, budgets, and activities. Transparency is a key principle in public governance, enabling open access to information for stakeholders. Research by Sari & Nugroho (2020) shows that transparency positively impacts accountability and organizational trust.

Accountability

Accountability is an organization's obligation to account for resource use and program implementation to stakeholders. In the school context, accountability includes financial reporting, program evaluation, and regulatory compliance. Accountability relates to an organization's obligation to be accountable for its performance and resource use. Pratama et al. (2022) found that strong accountability can improve the effectiveness of educational organizational management.

Participation

Participation refers to the active involvement of stakeholders in the decision-making process. In school management, teacher and school committee participation is a crucial indicator of democratic governance. However, several studies indicate that participation is often formal and does not significantly impact decision quality. Participation reflects active involvement in decision-making. Hidayat & Rahman (2021) state that symbolic participation does not significantly impact decision quality.

School Management Effectiveness

The effectiveness of school management reflects the level of success in achieving organizational goals. This includes program achievement, good coordination, and the ability to resolve problems efficiently. Effectiveness is greatly influenced by the quality of governance implemented within the organization. Organizational effectiveness is influenced by the quality of governance. Mulyono et al. (2021) emphasized that the principles of good governance contribute to increasing the effectiveness of school management.

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

METHOD

This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, consisting of two main stages.

A. Quantitative Stage

Data were collected through questionnaires distributed to 43 respondents: 12 from private high schools and 31 from public high schools.

The respondents had varying service periods ranging from 2 months to 33 years.

Length of service at the current school (written in numbers, for example: if 2 years then write the number 2).

The respondents consisted of the Principal, Vice Principal, teachers and education staff.

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

The instrument uses a Likert scale with 20 statements covering the variables of transparency, accountability, participation, and effectiveness. Each indicator consists of five statements:

Transparency

- The school communicates work program information openly to teachers.
- Teachers can access information on school budget usage.
- School activity reports are submitted clearly and regularly.
- No important information related to school management is withheld.
- Teachers receive adequate explanations regarding school policies.

Accountability (5 Points)

- The school maintains a clear accountability report for the use of funds.
- The school budget is used in accordance with established plans.
- Every school program is evaluated periodically.
- School leadership is responsible for every policy adopted.
- Program evaluation results are used for future improvements.

Participation (5 Points)

- Teachers are involved in school program planning.
- Teachers' opinions are considered in decision-making.
- School meetings provide opportunities for teachers to provide input.
- Communication between leaders and teachers is two-way.
- Teachers feel they have a role in determining the direction of school policy.

School Management Effectiveness (5 Points)

- School programs are implemented according to established plans.
- School activity targets are generally achieved.
- Coordination between school departments is effective.
- Problems in school management are resolved quickly.
- In general, school management is effective.

Data analysis is carried out through:

1. Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to describe the characteristics of the research data, including the average value, standard deviation, and distribution of respondents' answers to each variable.

2. Validity and reliability test

Validity tests are used to determine the level of accuracy of each statement item in measuring the variables being studied, while reliability tests are used to measure the consistency of the research instrument.

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

3. Linear regression analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis was used to determine the influence of the independent variables, namely transparency, accountability, and participation, on the dependent variable, namely the effectiveness of school management. Testing was conducted using a partial test (t-test) to determine the influence of each variable individually, and a simultaneous test (F-test) to determine the influence of the variables together. In addition, the coefficient of determination (R^2) was used to determine the extent of the independent variables' contribution to the dependent variable.

B. Qualitative Stage

The qualitative phase was conducted to explain the quantitative results. Informants were purposively selected from 2–3 schools in the research area. Data collection was conducted through:

- In-depth interviews
- Documentation study

Data analysis used thematic analysis through the following processes: transcription, coding, categorization, and theme formation.

Data validity was ensured through:

1. Source triangulation
Source triangulation was carried out by comparing data obtained from various informants, such as school principals, teachers, and administrative staff, so that a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon being studied was obtained.
2. Engineering triangulation
Technical triangulation is carried out by comparing data obtained through various data collection methods, such as questionnaires, interviews, and documentation, to ensure the consistency of the information obtained.
3. Member check
Member checking is conducted by reconfirming the interview results with the informant to ensure that the data obtained aligns with the informant's intentions and experiences. This technique aims to increase the credibility and accuracy of the research data.

C. Data Integration

Data integration was conducted using an explanatory sequential approach, where qualitative data was used to deepen and explain quantitative results to achieve a comprehensive understanding. Data integration in this study was conducted by combining the results of quantitative and qualitative analyses. Quantitative results obtained through questionnaires were used to identify patterns of relationships between variables, while qualitative data from interviews were used to deepen and explain these findings.

Integration was carried out at the interpretation stage by comparing and linking the results of the regression analysis with the interview findings. Qualitative data was used to explain why certain variables did or did not influence the effectiveness of school management. Thus, data integration provides a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomena studied, based not only on numerical data but also on the context and experiences of informants in the field.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Quantitative Stage

1. Descriptive Statistics
Descriptive statistical analysis was used to provide an overview of the research data, including the average value and distribution of respondents' responses to each variable. The analysis results indicate that the transparency, accountability, participation, and effectiveness of school management variables are in the relatively high category. This is evident from the predominance of respondents' responses on a scale of 4 and 5. The participation variable has the highest average value compared to the other variables, indicating that the level of stakeholder involvement in school management is quite good. Meanwhile, transparency and accountability also show high average values, but there is still variation in responses, indicating that their implementation is not yet even.

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

The transparency variable has an average value of 21.23; accountability 21.79; participation 22.02; and school management effectiveness 21.70. These values indicate that all variables are in the high category. In general, the results of descriptive statistics show that respondents' perceptions of the application of good governance principles in school management are in the good category.

- 2. Validity and reliability test
 - a) Transparency Variable
 - i. Validity test

		Correlations				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Pearson Correlation	1	.790**	.847**	.619**	.838**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<,001	<,001	<,001	<,001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
2	Pearson Correlation	.790**	1	.786**	.566**	.646**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<,001		<,001	<,001	<,001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
3	Pearson Correlation	.847**	.786**	1	.637**	.837**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<,001	<,001		<,001	<,001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
4	Pearson Correlation	.619**	.566**	.637**	1	.599**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<,001	<,001	<,001		<,001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
5	Pearson Correlation	.838**	.646**	.837**	.599**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<,001	<,001	<,001	<,001	
	N	43	43	43	43	43

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The validity test results showed that all items had correlation values greater than the table's r (0.301). Inter-item correlations ranged from 0.566 to 0.847, with a significance level of 0.000 (<0.05). This indicates that all items in the research instrument have a strong and significant relationship, thus being declared valid and suitable for use in research.

- ii. Reliability test

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.921	5

The reliability test results showed a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.921. This value is above 0.90, categorizing the research instrument as highly reliable. This indicates that all items in the instrument have a very high level of consistency and are suitable for use in research.

- b) Accountability Variables
 - i. Validity test

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

		Correlations				
		A1	A2	A3	A4	A5
A1	Pearson Correlation	1	.825**	.750**	.731**	.810**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
A2	Pearson Correlation	.825**	1	.831**	.771**	.860**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
A3	Pearson Correlation	.750**	.831**	1	.780**	.863**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
A4	Pearson Correlation	.731**	.771**	.780**	1	.833**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
A5	Pearson Correlation	.810**	.860**	.863**	.833**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	43	43	43	43	43

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results of the validity test on the accountability variable showed that all items had correlation values greater than the r table (0.301). The correlation values between items ranged from 0.731 to 0.863 with a significance level of 0.000 (<0.05). This shows that all items in the accountability variable have a strong and significant relationship, so they are declared valid and suitable for use in research.

ii. Reliability test

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.951	5

The reliability test results showed a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.951. This value is above 0.90, categorizing the research instrument as highly reliable. This indicates that all items in the instrument have a very high level of consistency and are suitable for use in research.

c) Participation Variable

i. Validity test

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

		Correlations				
		P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
P1	Pearson Correlation	1	.898**	.900**	.462**	.732**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	.002	<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
P2	Pearson Correlation	.898**	1	.886**	.373*	.742**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	.014	<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
P3	Pearson Correlation	.900**	.886**	1	.480**	.694**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		.001	<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
P4	Pearson Correlation	.462**	.373*	.480**	1	.476**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.014	.001		.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
P5	Pearson Correlation	.732**	.742**	.694**	.476**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	.001	
	N	43	43	43	43	43

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results of the validity test on the participation variable showed that all items had correlation values greater than the table's r (0.301). Correlations between items ranged from 0.373 to 0.900, with a significance level of <0.05.

Although one item had a relatively lower correlation value than the others, all items were still considered valid because they met the validity criteria. This indicates that all items adequately measured the participation variable.

Differences in correlation strength between items indicate variations in the contribution of each item to representing the participation construct, but overall, they remained within the valid category.

ii. Reliability test

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.897	5

The results of the reliability test on the participation variable showed a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.897. This value is greater than 0.70, thus declaring the instrument reliable. This indicates that the items in the participation variable have a very good level of consistency.

d) School Management Effectiveness Variables

i. Validity test

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

		Correlations				
		E1	E2	E3	E4	E5
E1	Pearson Correlation	1	.754**	.670**	.689**	.802**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
E2	Pearson Correlation	.754**	1	.651**	.711**	.693**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
E3	Pearson Correlation	.670**	.651**	1	.747**	.886**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
E4	Pearson Correlation	.689**	.711**	.747**	1	.764**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	43	43	43	43	43
E5	Pearson Correlation	.802**	.693**	.886**	.764**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	43	43	43	43	43

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The validity test results for the school management effectiveness variable showed that all items had correlation values greater than the table's r (0.301). The correlation values between items ranged from 0.651 to 0.886, with a significance level of 0.000 (<0.05).

This indicates that all items in the school management effectiveness variable have a strong and significant relationship, thus being declared valid and suitable for use in research.

ii. Reliability test

The reliability test results showed a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.932. This value is above 0.90, categorizing the research instrument as highly reliable. This indicates that all items in the instrument have a very high level of consistency and are suitable for use in research.

3. Linear regression analysis

i. Normality test

	Tests of Normality					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Efektivitas Pengelolaan Sekolah	.145	43	.024	.841	43	<.001
Transparansi	.222	43	<.001	.779	43	<.001
Akuntabilitas	.217	43	<.001	.707	43	<.001
Partisipasi	.195	43	<.001	.771	43	<.001
Unstandardized Residual	.146	43	.022	.976	43	.501

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The results of the Shapiro-Wilk normality test showed a significance value of 0.501 (>0.05). Thus, the residuals in this study were normally distributed and met the assumptions for regression analysis.

ii. Multiple linear regression analysis

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.881	1.554		3.784	<.001
	Transparansi	.242	.163	.328	1.486	.145
	Akuntabilitas	.167	.198	.222	.842	.405
	Partisipasi	.320	.158	.359	2.020	.050

a. Dependent Variable: Efektivitas Pengelolaan Sekolah

Based on the analysis results, the following regression equation was obtained:

$$Y = 5.881 + 0.242X_1 + 0.167X_2 + 0.320X_3$$

This equation indicates that transparency, accountability, and participation have a positive influence on the effectiveness of school management.

iii. Partial test (t-test)

The partial test results indicate that:

- 1) Transparency has a significance value of 0.145 (>0.05), so it has no significant effect.
- 2) Accountability has a significance value of 0.405 (>0.05), so it has no significant effect.
- 3) Participation has a significance value of 0.050 (≤0.05), so it has a significant effect on school management effectiveness.

This indicates that only the participation variable has a significant partial effect.

iv. Simultaneous test (F test)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	307.290	3	102.430	42.598	<.001 ^b
	Residual	93.779	39	2.405		
	Total	401.070	42			

a. Dependent Variable: Efektivitas Pengelolaan Sekolah
b. Predictors: (Constant), Partisipasi, Transparansi, Akuntabilitas

The F-test results show a calculated F-value of 42.598 with a significance level of 0.000 (<0.05). This indicates that transparency, accountability, and participation simultaneously have a significant effect on the effectiveness of school management.

v. Coefficient of determination (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.875 ^a	.766	.748	1.551

a. Predictors: (Constant), Partisipasi, Transparansi, Akuntabilitas
b. Dependent Variable: Efektivitas Pengelolaan Sekolah

The coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.766 shows that the variables of transparency, accountability, and participation are able to explain 76.6% of the effectiveness of school management, while the remaining 23.4% is influenced by other factors outside the research.

B. Qualitative Stage

Source triangulation

The validity of the data in this study was tested through source triangulation, comparing information obtained from various informants, including the principal, teachers, and administrative staff.

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

Interview results indicated a concordance of views among informants regarding the implementation of the principles of transparency, accountability, and participation in school management. The principal stated that management was conducted openly and involved various parties, a finding further reinforced by statements from teachers who felt involved in the planning and implementation of school programs.

Meanwhile, administrative staff also confirmed that the reporting and administration systems were operating according to established procedures. This concordance of information from various sources indicates a high level of reliability of the data obtained.

Engineering triangulation

In addition to source triangulation, data validity was also strengthened through technical triangulation, which involved comparing data from questionnaires, interviews, and documentation.

The questionnaire results indicated that the participation variable had the highest score compared to other variables. This finding was reinforced by interview results, which showed that teachers and staff were involved in various school activities, such as meetings, program planning, and activity evaluation.

Available documentation, such as meeting minutes and activity reports, also demonstrated the involvement of various parties in decision-making. Thus, there was consistency between the quantitative and qualitative data, strengthening the research findings.

Member check

Data validity was also ensured through member checking, which involved reconfirming the interview results with the informants. The informants were given the opportunity to review the researcher's interpretation of the answers they had provided. The results indicated that the informants agreed with and considered the interpretations to be consistent with the actual situation. This process ensured that the data used in the study accurately represented the informants' views and experiences.

C. Data Integration

This study used a mixed methods approach, integrating quantitative and qualitative data to gain a more comprehensive understanding of school management.

The quantitative analysis showed that simultaneously, the variables of transparency, accountability, and participation significantly influenced the effectiveness of school management. However, only the participation variable had a significant effect, while transparency and accountability did not.

These findings were further deepened through qualitative analysis. Interviews indicated that participation was the most dominant factor supporting the effectiveness of school management. Teachers and education personnel were actively involved in program planning, implementation, and evaluation, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility for the success of school programs.

Meanwhile, qualitatively, transparency and accountability were implemented, but tended to be administrative in nature. While program and financial information was available, it was not fully utilized as a basis for collective decision-making. Consequently, these two variables did not have a statistically significant effect on the effectiveness of school management.

Thus, the data integration results demonstrate a congruence between quantitative and qualitative findings, particularly regarding the participation variable, which has been shown to be a key factor in improving school management effectiveness.

The discrepancy between the quantitative and qualitative results for the transparency and accountability variables indicates that although both variables have been implemented in schools, their implementation has not been optimal in directly impacting management effectiveness.

Quantitatively, neither variable has a significant impact, but qualitatively, transparency and accountability have been implemented in the form of reporting and information dissemination. This indicates a gap between formal implementation and substantial utilization in school management practices.

This discrepancy can be understood as an indication that transparency and accountability are not strong enough to drive effectiveness without the active participation of all stakeholders.

Therefore, the data integration in this study not only strengthens the findings but also provides a deeper understanding of the factors influencing the effectiveness of school management.

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

The Influence of Transparency on School Management Effectiveness

The results of this study indicate that transparency does not significantly impact the effectiveness of school management. Although the descriptive transparency score is high, partial test results indicate that transparency has not significantly contributed to improving the effectiveness of school management.

This finding indicates that the transparency implemented in schools is still administrative in nature, such as the dissemination of program information and financial reports, but has not been optimally utilized as a basis for collective decision-making. This is reinforced by interview results, which indicated that the information provided is not fully understood or utilized by all stakeholders.

Thus, formal transparency is insufficient to promote effective school management if it is not accompanied by the active use of information in the managerial process.

The Influence of Accountability on School Management Effectiveness

The results of this study indicate that accountability does not significantly impact the effectiveness of school management. Although theoretically, accountability is an important principle in organizational management, in the context of this study, its implementation has not yet had a tangible impact.

Based on interviews, accountability has been implemented in the form of activity and financial reporting. However, this reporting tends to be formal and has not been used as evaluation material to improve the quality of school management.

This indicates that accountability that is solely focused on reporting has not been able to improve the effectiveness of school management without follow-up in the form of evaluation and continuous improvement.

The Influence of Participation on School Management Effectiveness

Unlike other variables, participation significantly impacts school management effectiveness. This indicates that the active involvement of teachers and education staff is a key factor in successful school management.

Interviews revealed that teachers are involved in various activities, such as program planning, meetings, and activity evaluation. This involvement fosters a sense of ownership in school programs, thus encouraging more effective program implementation.

These findings indicate that participation is not just attendance at activities, but also active involvement in the decision-making process which has a direct impact on the effectiveness of school management.

The Simultaneous Effect of Transparency, Accountability, and Participation

The results of the simultaneous test indicate that transparency, accountability, and participation collectively have a significant effect on the effectiveness of school management. This indicates that these three variables are integral in the implementation of good governance principles.

Although not all variables have a significant partial effect, collectively, they contribute significantly to the effectiveness of school management. This demonstrates a complementary relationship between the variables.

Integrative Discussion (Quantitative and Qualitative)

The results of the study indicate a congruence between the quantitative and qualitative data. Quantitatively, participation was proven to be the variable most influential on the effectiveness of school management. This finding is supported by qualitative results, which indicate that active stakeholder involvement is a key factor in successful school management.

Meanwhile, transparency and accountability, which did not have a significant quantitative impact, are explained by qualitative findings, which indicate that the implementation of these two variables is still administrative in nature and does not directly impact effectiveness.

Thus, this study demonstrates that the effectiveness of school management is not solely determined by the formal application of good governance principles, but rather by the extent to which these principles are substantively implemented, particularly through active participation.

The findings of this study confirm that participation is a key factor in increasing the effectiveness of school management, while transparency and accountability need to be improved in terms of implementation quality so that they are not only administrative in nature, but also have a real impact on school management.

THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research conducted using a mixed methods approach, the following conclusions can be drawn: Transparency does not significantly impact the effectiveness of school management. Although implemented, transparency tends to be administrative in nature and has not been optimally utilized in the decision-making process. Accountability does not significantly impact the effectiveness of school management. Accountability implementation still focuses on formal reporting and has not been fully utilized as a basis for evaluating and improving school management. Participation significantly influences the effectiveness of school management. The active involvement of teachers and education personnel in program planning, implementation, and evaluation has been shown to improve the effectiveness of school management. Simultaneously, transparency, accountability, and participation significantly influence the effectiveness of school management, indicating that these three variables are essential for implementing good governance principles. The results of the integration of quantitative and qualitative data indicate that participation is the dominant factor in increasing the effectiveness of school management, while transparency and accountability still need to be improved in their implementation to achieve a more tangible impact.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results, several recommendations can be made as follows:

- 1) For Schools
Schools are expected to improve the quality of their transparency and accountability implementation, not only in the form of administrative reporting, but also as a basis for decision-making involving all stakeholders. Furthermore, schools need to maintain and increase the active participation of teachers and education personnel in every school management process, as this has been proven to have a significant impact on effectiveness.
- 2) For School Principals
School principals are expected to foster a participatory culture in school management by providing greater opportunity for teachers and staff to participate in decision-making. Principals also need to ensure that transparency and accountability are not merely formal but are genuinely utilized as tools to improve the school's organizational performance.
- 3) For Future Researchers
Further researchers are advised to add other variables that could potentially influence the effectiveness of school management, such as leadership, organizational culture, and human resource competency. Furthermore, future research could use a larger sample size or a broader regional scope to obtain more generalizable results.
- 4) For Policymakers
Policymakers in the education sector are expected to formulate policies that encourage the substantive implementation of good governance principles, particularly by increasing the active participation of all stakeholders in school management.

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THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLES (TRANSPARENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, AND PARTICIPATION) ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL MIXED METHODS STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN EAST KALIMANTAN

Irriyanti et al

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